

dist.class	coef	p.value	n
3.959	0.638	0.00e+00	1338576
11.712	0.383	0.00e+00	2080136
19.465	0.120	0.00e+00	2130268
27.218	-0.088	1.00e+00	1904600
34.971	-0.124	1.00e+00	1521748
42.724	-0.087	1.00e+00	1249776
50.477	-0.036	1.00e+00	826122
58.230	-0.007	9.97e-01	700014
65.983	-0.082	1.00e+00	620488
73.736	-0.147	1.00e+00	450760
81.489	-0.092	1.00e+00	389964
89.242	-0.004	7.70e-01	304982
96.995	0.097	1.50e-81	255992
104.748	0.157	1.13e-137	154706
112.501	0.116	1.01e-37	93076
120.254	0.116	3.57e-38	42100
128.007	-0.118	1.00e+00	19670
135.760	-0.172	1.00e+00	20220
143.513	-0.243	1.00e+00	7098
151.266	-1.037	1.00e+00	996